

VALUABLE

VALORISATION OF FUNGAL BIOMASS USING NOVEL ENZYMATIC TECHNOLOGY

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Contributing partners	BioLog
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The present deliverable has already been approved by the European Commission and has been uploaded to VALUABLE's CORDIS website: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059786>